

PLAN'EAT

Guidelines for mapping food environments across Europe

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1. What are food environments?

The food environment is quite a novel concept, giving rise to multiple definitions. Initial definitions focused on the external dimensions of the environment, such as stores and neighbourhoods. Later definitions tried to include the personal dimensions of consumers. Different disciplines formulate the underlying dimensions differently. Hence, we follow Turner et al. (2018)'s attempt at harmonizing the definition of food environments, building on the FAO (2016) report *Influencing food environments for healthy diets* and rooted in socio-ecological theory. They define the food environment as follows:

“the interface that mediates people’s food acquisition and consumption within the wider food system. It encompasses external dimensions such as the availability, prices, vendor and product properties, and promotional information; and personal dimensions such as the accessibility, affordability, convenience, and desirability of food sources and products” (Turner et al., 2018, p 95).

What is critical here is that food **environments result from the interaction between external and personal domains and are part of broader food systems** (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual model of the food environment

Thus, **there is not one food environment in a given situation, but every individual has their food environment, particularly as individuals experience the food environment differently.** Hence, to be able to identify problematic areas in the food environment that are inhibiting people from engaging in healthy and sustainable diets, **it is important to analyze the food environment through the lens of consumers' lived experiences.**

There are several methods to analyze consumers' lived experiences, including individual interviews, group discussions, visual methods, geospatial methods, and diaries (Neve et al., 2021).

We propose a mixed-method approach to be able to go deeper into perceptions and motivations, eliciting narratives, and at the same time also be conscious of the time and resources available for this task. This document presents the minimum requirement for the task, and each Living Lab is invited to go deeper if possible - and to prepare publications and dissemination materials based on the task's results.

2. Overview of the methodology

A three steps mixed-methodological package allow us to gather (1) quantitative data on food environments together with (2) qualitative data on the participant's subjective experiences and perceptions through guided visual story-telling. The qualitative methodology builds on the dimensions of the quantitative survey to gain a deeper, more reflective understanding of food environments.

1. Quantitative methods:

NEMS-P survey: Participants will complete the validated questionnaire following the researchers' instructions.

2. Qualitative-participatory methods:

Part 1: Photovoice: Participants will be trained to take pictures based on the researchers' instructions. 5 pictures will be selected for further discussion.

Part 2: Focus group: Participants will be asked to join a focus group discussion to talk about their food environment via photos. Questions are prepared to cover all the dimensions we wish to gather data on.

This methodology is intended to be repeated every year of the project. A review will be done based on the Living Labs' feedback on of the piloting phase.

Aims:

- 1) critically consider the role of the food environment in shaping their and their families' consumption practices,
- 2) determine what the strengths and weaknesses of the food environment are,
- 3) propose areas for change that were grounded in their lived experiences.

Isaacs A. et al. (2022) Gathering data on food environments and food practices through photo elicitation in Copenhagen, Denmark: Implications for adapting the EAT- LANCET reference diet to local circumstances, CITIES & HEALTH

Needed Resources:

NEMS-P Survey

- Translating questionnaire
- 10-20 minutes survey with 20 citizens
- Input data from interviews if needed

Photovoice

- Translating materials and questions
- 2x60-90 min session with 6-6 citizens
- Gathering and printing pictures

Focus Group Discussion

- Translating materials questions
- 2x120 min session with 6-6 citizens
- Transcription and filling in the reporting template

3. NEMS-P questionnaire

The conceptual model of NEMS-P is an extension of the Model of Community Nutrition Environments described by Glanz and colleagues in 2005.

The research we intend to conduct is exploratory and our goal is to characterize the food environment that the LLs' target groups experience every day.

The questionnaire comprises 39 items:

- 5 questions on the home food environment;
- 11 questions on food shopping;
- 6 restaurant/eating out questions;
- 9 questions on eating habits;
- 1 general household question;
- 6 background questions.

Summary of procedure

The first phase of the study will consist of a pilot testing that will involve minimum of 5 individuals.

Following the pilot testing phase, the second phase of the study will be the main measurement study. In this phase of the study, 20 subjects from the selected target group will complete the questionnaire.

Recruitment Method

Sampling quota method will be adopted: the selection of subjects is by simple random sampling once the categories have been created.

As far as LLs involving minors are concerned, the questionnaire will be addressed to their parents.

The table below shows our selection criteria proposal for each LL.

With the face-to-face meetings, we will have the opportunity to discuss the selection criteria and adapt the questionnaire questions to the chosen target groups and the characteristics of the country where the LLs take place.

Country	Target group	SES	Health status	Selection criteria
<i>Greece</i>	Elderly People (>60)	all	Healthy	Elderly people/ all SES/ health status
<i>Sweden</i>	Toddlers (<6)	middle/high	Healthy	Toddlers` parents, with middle/high SES/ health status
<i>France</i>	Children and adolescents (6-15)	middle/high	Healthy	Children and adolescents` parents, with middle/high SES/ health status
<i>Germany</i>	Children and adolescents (10-20)	all	Obese	Children and adolescents` parents, with all SES/ with obese children
<i>Poland</i>	Children and adolescents (1-16)	low	Healthy	Children and adolescents` parents, with low SES/ with health children
<i>Italy</i>	Adults (18-70)	low	Diabetic	Adults/low SES
<i>Spain</i>	Adults (40-85)	low	Healthy	Adults/low SES/ health status
<i>Hungary</i>	Single Parents (>18)	low	Healthy	Single parents/low SES/ health status
<i>Ireland</i>	Young Adults (18-30)	all	Healthy	Young adults/all SES/ health status

Participants access the surveys using a mobile device

4. Participatory methodologies

Part 1. Photovoice

Learn about photovoice

Take photographs (2 days)

Share 5 outstanding images with the researchers

Part 2. Focusgroups

Share and discuss your experiences in a focus group setting

Researchers fill in the data collection reporting template

The combined methodological approach allows the researchers to include the availability, accessibility, price, and socio-cultural aspects and promotion of **environmental food provisioning and environmental practices of the participants**.

The **qualitative-participatory methods** will complement the quantitative method and **reflect on 3 food environments** (home food environment, food shopping/procurement/home-growing environment, and eating-out environment) that are integrated into the survey.

Out of the 20 people who participated in the quantitative part, 12 will be invited to continue the journey and take part both in the photovoice and focus group sessions.

4. Methodological overview

Photovoice

Photovoice is a qualitative and participatory methodology commonly practiced with a group of people or a place-based community through digital or analog photographing. In the photovoice method, researchers and social workers use photos to generate discussion and storytelling and deconstruct specific issues by asking questions. It is often used in community development to capture individual communities' wishes, desires, expectations, and overlooked knowledge.

Timeframe: 60-90 min per session

Number of participants: 6 - 6

participants per session

Number of sessions: 2

How to prepare for the photovoice workshop session?

Step 1: Select a moderator from your team (if necessary, a co-moderator or a note-taker)

Step 2: Recruit and choose 6-12 participants who will be participating

Step 3: Preparation for the session

Step 4: Preparation for photovoice educational part

Step 5: Preparation for the task

Step 6: Preparation for the focus group

**METHODOLOGY GUIDANCE AT POINT 7
FACILITATION GUIDANCE [HERE](#)**

Focus group

A focus group is a qualitative research method that brings together a group of people (6-12 people) to answer questions and interact in a moderated setting. This setting allows the researcher to obtain more data than from individual interviews. Moreover, it also leaves room for the researcher to observe the group's dynamics, reactions, and participants' body language, which could lead to further research directions.

Timeframe: 120 min per session

Number of participants: 6 - 6

participants per session

Number of sessions: 2

How to prepare for the focus group discussion session?

Step 1: The moderators and note-takers of the photovoice workshop will be present

Step 2: Prepare for the discussion by translating & adapting the focus group facilitation guide

Step 3: Set up your focus group

Step 4: Flow of the discussion

Step 5: Analyze your data and report your results

**METHODOLOGY GUIDANCE AT POINT 7
FACILITATION GUIDANCE [HERE](#)**

5. Sharing the results with participants

After citizens have engaged in the participatory research process, it is highly important to create opportunities for them to learn about the results of their co-produced work. Creating space for this also helps to bring closure to the process and to disseminate the co-created knowledge to a wider audience.

Each LL is invited to design and organize dissemination events that best fit their process and context. We are happy to provide methodological support for this both during the 1-on-1-s and at a later stage of the process if needed. Below you can find the most important aims of the event, as well as some ideas to get started.

Main aims:

Share results with participants

Allow participants to feel part of something greater
- connecting labs in different locations

Disseminate the results at a local level

Showcase our project in Brussels

Ideas for dissemination:

"Travelling" Exhibition -

showcasing all pictures of made in the 9 LLs in each location

Culinary Experience

Connecting the sharing of the research results with cooking together/eating together with participants

Thematic Session @ the STS conf in Graz (8-10 May)

F.2 From the edge to the core: participatory food environment research in European cities

Abstract submission by January 30!

Joint Publications

6. Timeframe and deliverables

1. Conducting interviews with 20 Citizens
2. Photovoice introduction session (2x 60-90 min)
1. Maximum two weeks for individual data collection (citizens take pictures)
2. Final focus group sessions (2x 120 min)
3. Transcription, translation, entering questionnaire data and filling in the reporting template

Final deadline for sending back the results of phase 1 & 2!

1. **First week of January:** pre-final version of the protocol sent out
2. **From mid-January to mid-February:** LLs training sessions on the protocol, separately with each Lab
3. **From mid-January to the end of February:**
 - Each LL pilots adapts and translates the questionnaire
 - Translates all materials necessary for the photovoice preparation session and the focus group

7. Methodology guide: Photovoice

In the **photovoice method**, researchers and social workers use photos to generate discussion and storytelling and deconstruct specific issues by asking questions. The primary purpose of this methodology is:

- (1) to provide the participants with technical and artistic knowledge,
- (2) to encourage them to visually explore and represent their lived experiences, living environment, and neighborhood,
- (3) to flesh out their stories through their photos in a focus group session.

Step 1: Select a moderator from your team (if necessary a co-moderator or a note-taker)

Facilitation: It is a key component of this methodology. Carefully select the person(s) who will lead the meeting, coordinate the technology (voice recorder), take notes and monitor the group dynamics. If this seems to be a challenging task for one person, you can appoint a co-facilitator to help with the process.

Ideally, the moderators should represent as many genders and ages as possible to create a safe space for the participants. Some participants may prefer to share information with women rather than men, or younger researchers may not necessarily be listened to simply because of their age.

Best case: The selected moderators may already have established connections or have been in contact with the potential participants. See Step 5 for further guidance on moderation.

The moderators speak clearly, without using abstract concepts and questions. Bear in mind along the process to ask questions effectively in a way that brings forward local perspectives. This is done through open-ended questions (e.g., Why? What? When? Where? Who? And How?) and by probing further, asking for examples and more information.

Step 2: Recruit and choose 12 people who will be participating in the sessions

Selection: To select the participants from your target group, you first need to ensure that those who have expressed an interest in participating in the programme are willing to do so. You will get better results if participants are active and have creative ideas for photos. *You can invite more than 12 people, as some might leave the research process earlier.* At this stage, you briefly inform them about the research, their responsibilities and incentives (common lunch, snacks, photo-related activities, potential exhibition etc.).

Consent form: When they confirm their participation, inform them about possible uses for their photos and their rights and responsibilities in a consent form. You share information on research ethics, the data collection process, usage of the collected data and their right to withdraw from the study at any time. Participants should also be guaranteed confidentiality and anonymity where possible. If the participants are under the age of 16 or 18, additional consent should be sought from their parents.

Step 3: Preparation for the session

Survey: Before the session, prepare a short oral or written survey on smartphone access. Some participants may not have one. Before organising the meeting, ensure all participants have a device (phone or camera) with which they can take photos.

Devices: Optionally, Polaroid cameras or smartphones can be purchased as incentives for workshops. You may also want to check with tech and phone companies for their smartphone and tablets products. They might be willing to support the research process by donating devices.

Step 4: Preparation for photovoice educational part

Setting: It is essential to create a safe and comfortable space for participants and to respect everyone's opinions and questions. For example, a table in the middle of settling in a circle where everyone can see each other and feel comfortable. The researcher sits next to the participants to create an eye-level conversation without reinforcing hierarchical differences between him/herself and the group.

Food and drinks: Ensure they have healthy snacks and drinks at the table when they arrive. Encourage them to serve themselves before you start the session. This can be a good way to set the topic and discuss their food-related practices. They can also start to think how to take pictures of food.

Taking pictures: The group of participants can be diverse regarding artistic ability. Therefore, basic photography training is essential to ensure they are all on the same page about the task. You need to make sure they understand their camera's functionality and that they can use it. Some good and bad examples help to illustrate what you expect from them. In the literature section, you can find examples of photovoice pictures in the listed publications that you can use to illustrate the task. After the demonstration, you can ask them to try to take pictures of the food on the table.

Ethics: The public nature of photography infringes on the privacy/anonymity of people. People, who agree to appear in a photo, or have a photo taken of their home, may not necessarily know what the captions and reflections that will accompany the photo will say. This makes photovoice an ethical minefield with potentially serious implications, requiring a number of considerations to be made. These include:

- When taking a picture, one has to be careful about not intruding into one's private space, whether that means taking a picture of someone's home or a picture of a person.
- Being careful about not disclosing embarrassing facts about individuals. It would, for example, be inappropriate to take a photograph of someone doing something that may incriminate them or if they are in a compromised position (e.g., sick and bedridden)
- Being careful about not giving individuals a false impression by refraining from telling them how the image will be used.
- Being aware of how local people will react to having their community/activities/home/food documented through photography.

A number of things can be done to **overcome some of these ethical dilemmas**. These include:

- Ensure that participants are adequately trained and sensitized on the ethical and GDPR implications of using photovoice in their setting.
- The participants must reflect on the ethical dilemmas of using photovoice in their setting and map out ways to overcome these challenges.
- If participants took a picture of someone and wanted to write a story that reflects poorly on them, or if participants decided not to take a picture because it would infringe on their personal space or disclose something embarrassing about them, they could draw a picture instead.
- It is important to sensitize local communities and families to the photovoice project, making them aware of its aims and objectives, and obtain collective consent for the project through the participants.
- The participants can also carry a brochure or information sheet (provided in word format) giving detail about the photovoice project, its aims and objectives while they are taking pictures.

GDPR: The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a set of rules that govern the processing of personal data of individuals within the European Union. Personal data is defined as any information that relates to an identified or identifiable individual, such as a name, email address, or photograph.

1. **Consent:** You must obtain explicit consent from individuals before taking their pictures and using their images. This means that you must inform them of your intention to take their picture and how you will use the image, and they must give their explicit consent before you proceed.
2. **Purpose limitation:** You must have a specific purpose for taking and using the pictures, which must be clearly defined and communicated to the individuals. You cannot use the images for any other purpose without obtaining additional consent.
3. **Data minimization:** You must only take and use as many pictures as necessary for the defined purpose. This means that you should not take unnecessary pictures or keep the images for longer than necessary.
4. **Data security:** You must ensure that the pictures are stored securely, and that access is restricted to those who need it for the defined purpose.
5. **Data subject rights:** Individuals have the right to access, rectify, erase, or restrict the processing of their images. They also have the right to object to the processing of their images and to withdraw their consent at any time.

To protect personal data, it is better to ask the participants to avoid taking pictures of faces and identifiable personal traits. Pictures in the food environment photovoice should be focused on objects, settings, food, prices, and interesting phenomenon. Otherwise, the consent of the persons appearing in the pictures needs to be required and documented.

Step 5: Preparation for the task

About the task: Ask participants to take pictures with their phone or camera for at least two days: one weekday and one weekend. Each participant should take at least 5 pictures of different food events: dining out, eating at home, grocery shopping, food preparation, food storage, food waste management, sharing food with others, and other food-related activities during the two days.

Ask them to take a picture that is a good example for them and one that evokes negative feelings. Prepare your pictures or download some for the education part. Show pictures to the group of what the expectation is the best way to prepare them.

A brief information sheet: We prepared a sheet that can help them to bear in mind the task or you can ask them to take a picture of your slide explaining the task. They might have questions and objections about the dates or the number of pictures. Try to explain why it is important for the research. We aim to gather more diverse pictures which reflect their food environments. If some situation you identified is challenging for some of them to grasp, ask them to draw or take notes instead of pictures. The printed sheet serves as proof of the task. In case someone stops them, they can always show the information sheet.

Step 6: Preparation for the focus group

Sharing pictures: Ask each participant to share the **minimum 5 pictures** they have taken with the researcher via email, social media or the online platform you use for interactions. After you have chosen the platform together, make sure you remind them to send the picture and also the expectations (see the prepared information sheet). Remember that you need 3-5 days of preparation for the focus group.

Receiving pictures: When you receive the pictures, ensure you screened all the pictures from a GDPR point of view and selected the **5 pictures**. If you do not find any issues, prepare the pictures for printing or screening for the focus group.

If you find something is against the GDPR or you find it unethical, communicate with the participant in question and kindly ask to replace the problematic pictures. If it is not possible, they can possibly accept with minimum 3 pictures.

After receiving the pictures: you can share them with the participants. They can come prepared for the focus group session. You can share with them the possible utilisation of the photos (online or physical exhibition, blog posts, publications, comic books etc.). Anything goes as far as you have a budget for it and the group expressed their interest. If the participants are against it, you do not have to force it.

7. Methodology guide: focus group

Step 1: Moderators & note-takers of the photovoice workshop are present

Facilitation and data collection works best when trust is established with the participants. Better results - i.e. better stories - are obtained when the relationship between facilitators, note-takers and participants has been established beforehand.

If, for some reason, the photovoice moderators or note-takers cannot lead the focus group, make sure they prepare an icebreaker and take the time to introduce themselves in person. Former moderators should also introduce their successors by email before the meeting, ensuring that participants have time to get to know the new moderators.

Step 2: Prepare for the discussion by translating & adapting the focus group facilitation guide

Before you start the session, make sure that the list of questions has been translated and adapted to your specific beneficiary group. Ideally, the main facilitator will lead the session with open questions (see the "[Focus Group Facilitation Guide](#)" for further support) and let the participants create their own stories based on the images they brought. The note taker can follow the process closely and jump in at the end with guiding questions related to dimensions that have not come up in the discussion.

Step 3: Set up the Focus Group

Setting: It is essential to create a safe and comfortable space for participants and to respect everyone's opinions and questions. For example, a table in the middle of settling in a circle where everyone can see each other and feel comfortable. The researcher sits next to the participants to create an eye-level conversation without reinforcing hierarchical differences between him/herself and the group.

Materials: Ensure they have healthy snacks and drinks at the table when they arrive. Encourage them to serve themselves before you start the session. This can be a good way to set the topic and discuss their food-related practices.

Also make sure that the pictures are printed, as well as that there are papers and utensils to draw with.

Step 4: Flow of the discussion

Make sure to encourage and allow discussion and sharing, especially the development of narratives and stories around the chosen pictures.

Facilitating this type of participatory process is like carefully shaping the banks of a small river or stream. Ideally, you would like to allow it to flow freely, discovering landscapes - themes - relevant to the participants. At the same time, as a facilitator, it is your role to make sure that all important fields are watered and no village gets flooded. Meaning that if some dimensions (see in the reporting template) were not discussed, you need to guide the conversation to cover all bases, while if the participants venture off to completely unrelated topics you need to invite them back to focus. It can bring great enjoyment when you can do this in an almost invisible way, without abrupt course corrections. The order of the questions and dimensions do not matter, you can bring in the themes that are most suitable at any given moment.

In addition, try to make sure that all participants have the opportunity to share their opinions.

Dimensions: The note-taker can pay more attention to which **dimensions** and issues were discussed and help to raise the missed questions. The questions can be asked differently, rephrased and edited for the sake of the better flow of the conversation, but keep in mind that you need to cover all dimensions. If some dimensions, e.g. social aspect, come out stronger than others, you can allow participants to express their ideas and feelings about it. However, overall please make sure that there is rich data for the analyses.

Drawing the visions: Make sure to point out that it is not about artistic talent but rather about allowing their imaginations to bring in new aspects and to be able to visualize a desired future.

Ending the session: Ask the participants what else they would like to share and if they have anything to add or discuss. They may have questions for each other or the moderators. They may also have questions about the next step. At the end of the session, agree on how the photos will be used. This question was raised in the photovoice session. Clear options should be offered to the group to help them decide what to do with the photos together.

Step 5: Analyze your data and report your results

Reporting: Please fill in the reporting template (shared in a separate word document) using the focus group recording, notes and the discussion you have described. Direct quotes are needed as evidence, as well as the focus group leaders' comments and notes. Under the researcher's notes, we wish to get the analytical insights and observations made during the photovoice and focus group sessions. *For example, on the gender or family dynamics, the moderator or note-taker observed their emotional reactions.*

There may not be responses under all the dimensions listed in the reporting template. In this case, explain why it was not relevant and salient for the participants. For example, religion and ethnic traditions may be essential for someone. It may be mentioned by some participants, while others talked about it at length.

Follow-up: In case of insufficient or poor quality data received from the LLs, the task 1.3 leaders may conduct follow-up interviews with the focus group facilitators and request access to the entire English transcript of the focus group. The above template assists LLs in bringing out the main discussion points and valuable data and preparing it for cross-case analysis.

Thank you for your collaboration & wishing you an enjoyable process!

8. Useful tools for implementations

For translations: DeepL: <https://www.deepl.com/translator>

For transcribing the recorded focus group: <https://otter.ai/>

For sending large files (pictures), only available in English: <https://wetransfer.com/>

Outsourcing the focus group questions to a larger group on Padlet:
<https://hu.padlet.com/dashboard>

To gather geolocation data on the food environment on Padlet:
<https://hu.padlet.com/dashboard>

Online timer with sound for the sessions: <https://vclock.com/timer/>

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9. Recommended literature

Food environment

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- Katare, B., Lynch, K., & Savaiano, D. (2021). Perceived neighborhood food environment and overweight and obesity among Supplemental Nutrition Assistance Program-Education (SNAP-Ed) participants in the Midwest US. *Public Health Nutrition*, 24(4), 729–737. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S136898002000155X>
- Kong, T. M., Kellner, K., Austin, D. E., Els, Y., & Orr, B. J. (2014). Society & Natural Resources An International Journal Enhancing Participatory Evaluation of Land Management through Photo Elicitation and Photovoice. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2014.941448>
- Moore, L. v., Diez Roux, A. v., & Brines, S. (2008). Comparing Perception-Based and Geographic Information System (GIS)-Based Characterizations of the Local Food Environment. *Journal of Urban Health*, 85(2), 206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11524-008-9259-X>
- Neve, K., Hawkes, C., Brock, J., Spires, M., Isaacs, A., Gallagher Squires, C., Sharpe, R., Bradbury, D., Battersby, J., Chaboud, G., Chung, A., Conaré, D., Coveney, J., Demmler, K., Dickinson, A., Diez, J., Holdsworth, M., Kimani-Murage, E., Laar, A., ... Zorbas Creative media by Gavin Wren, C. (2021). Understanding Lived Experience of Food Environments to Inform Policy: An Overview of Research Methods. www.city.ac.uk

Photovoice

- Understanding the local food environment: A participatory photovoice project in a low-income area in Madrid, Spain.
- Residents' perceptions of their local food environment in socioeconomically diverse neighborhoods: A photovoice study. Gravina L, Jauregi A, Estebanez A, Fernández-Aedo I, Guenaga N, Ballesteros-Peña S, Díez J, Franco M. *Appetite*. 2020 Apr 1;147:104543. doi: 10.1016/j.appet.2019.104543. Epub 2019 Nov 30. PMID: 31794819
- Residents' Insights on Their Local Food Environment and Dietary Behaviors: A Cross-City Comparison Using Photovoice in Spain, Leyre Gravina, Amets Jauregi, Irrintzi Fernández-Aedo, Julia Díez, Joel Gittelsohn, Uriyoan Colón-Ramos, and Manuel Franco, *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021 Oct; 18(19): 10134.

Focus group

- Toolkit for Conducting Focus Groups - Community Tool Box
- [Greenbaum, T. L. \(1999\). Moderating focus groups: A practical guide for group facilitation. Sage Publications.](#)

